

Key factors to learn when designing housing in the future

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summary

The future of housing design is increasingly shaped by a multitude of factors that address evolving societal needs, technological advancements, and sustainability imperatives. Central to this discourse are the Capability Approach (CA) and the Quality of Life Framework (QoLF), which advocate for enhancing individual freedoms and well-being through thoughtful design that fosters community, control, and connectivity in residential environments.^{[1][2]} The integration of smart home health technologies (SHHTs) is another pivotal element, particularly in catering to aging populations, as these innovations aim to improve the quality of life for older adults while addressing usability challenges that hinder widespread adoption.^{[3][4]}

Sustainability has emerged as a crucial consideration in modern housing, with an increasing demand for eco-friendly designs and materials that contribute to long-term cost savings and environmental resilience.^[5] However, financial constraints and misconceptions about sustainability as an added cost pose significant barriers to its implementation. Moreover, establishing clear standards and fostering collaboration among stakeholders are essential to overcome these challenges and promote widespread adoption of sustainable practices in housing design.^{[6][7]}

Despite the potential for innovative design solutions, the global housing landscape faces pressing challenges, including a severe affordability crisis that threatens millions with inadequate housing.^[8] Factors such as rising construction costs, urban inequalities, and supply chain constraints exacerbate this crisis, necessitating comprehensive strategies that prioritize affordability and accessibility.^{[9][10]} These issues underscore the importance of community engagement and inclusive design approaches that respect local identities and foster social cohesion amidst urban development pressures.^{[11][12]}

As housing design progresses into the future, it will be critical to embrace technological integration, adaptability, and resilience to external disruptors such as climate change and pandemics.^{[13][14]} By prioritizing user-centric principles and sustainable practices, architects and builders can create homes that not only meet contemporary demands but also contribute to a harmonious relationship between technology, community, and the environment, ensuring livable and equitable spaces for all.^{[15][16]}

Key Factors

Capability Approach and Quality of Life Framework

A crucial aspect in designing future housing is the integration of the Capability Approach (CA) alongside the Quality of Life Framework (QoLF). The CA emphasizes the importance of understanding the freedoms and opportunities available to individuals, framing resources as means to enhance well-being rather than ends in themselves[1]. This perspective aligns with the six broad dimensions defined by the QoLF: control, health, nature, wonder, movement, and community, which serve as a guideline for identifying key variables that reflect residents' capabilities in housing environments[1].

Community and Control Dimensions

The community dimension highlights the significance of public spaces, social identity, and the overall connectivity of neighborhoods[1]. Effective housing design should facilitate strong community ties, enabling residents to engage with their environment and each other. The control dimension focuses on the variety of housing options available, feelings of safety, and the involvement of residents in local decisions, all of which contribute to a sense of empowerment and agency[1].

Technology Integration for Elderly Care

Another vital factor is the incorporation of smart home health technologies (SHHTs) aimed at improving the quality of life for older adults. These technologies enable continuous monitoring of health-related parameters, thereby ensuring safety and providing peace of mind to both the elderly and their caregivers[2]. SHHTs can also facilitate communication, assist with daily activities, and support healthier lifestyles, which is particularly important for aging populations[2].

Customization and Usability Challenges

While SHHTs offer significant benefits, challenges such as obtrusiveness, usability, and social acceptance remain barriers to widespread adoption[2]. Effective design must prioritize user-centric solutions that accommodate the unique needs of older adults while ensuring that caregivers can efficiently monitor and respond to health-related issues.

Sustainability in Housing Design

Sustainability is increasingly becoming a focal point in housing design, as evidenced by recent trends that show a growing demand for green buildings[3][4]. This includes the use of sustainable materials, energy-efficient appliances, and water-saving features. However, financial constraints and misconceptions about sustainability being an added cost hinder its adoption[3]. A shift in perspective is necessary, emphasizing that sustainable practices can lead to long-term cost savings through efficient resource use and enhanced durability[3].

The Role of Standards and Policy

To effectively implement sustainable practices in housing design, the establishment of clear standards and guidance is essential. Tools like the RICS Whole Life Carbon Assessment aim to address these challenges by providing a framework for evaluating

sustainability throughout the lifecycle of a building[3]. Additionally, fostering collaboration among homeowners, manufacturers, and design professionals can create a shared commitment to sustainability in future housing projects[4].

Design Principles

Aesthetic Considerations

In the realm of luxury real estate, aesthetic appeal plays a significant role in attracting buyers and enhancing the perceived value of properties. By staying attuned to design trends, developers can create spaces that resonate with contemporary tastes. Projects like the Is Molas development exemplify how innovative design and aesthetic excellence can redefine living environments and elevate market desirability[5].

Evolving Interior Trends

The interior design landscape has shifted towards a more personalized and vibrant approach, moving away from overly minimalist aesthetics. Current trends embrace color, texture, and unique decorative elements, fostering spaces that provide warmth and meaning. This evolution reflects a growing preference for environments that resonate emotionally with their inhabitants, as architects leverage new technologies to enhance the livability and functionality of interior spaces[4][6].

User-Centric and Sustainable Perspectives

In modern housing design, integrating user-centric and sustainable perspectives is essential for creating environments that prioritize comfort, safety, and efficient use of resources. The Design Thinking (DT) approach, traditionally utilized in product design, emphasizes consumer empathy and rapid prototyping, which can be adapted to address broader challenges in smart home projects. However, a systematic literature review indicates that the DT approach has rarely been applied in this context, suggesting a gap that can be explored for future housing developments[7][8].

Morphological Matrix for Smart Homes

To enhance the design process for smart homes, a generic morphological matrix can be established based on parameters that encompass various user needs and technological capabilities. These parameters include entertainment and comfort, home automation, remote access, network security, healthcare services, resource efficiency, energy management, and property surveillance. This structured approach allows designers to create consistent alternative conceptions for smart homes that cater to both user preferences and sustainability goals[7].

Contextual Understanding

Effective design decisions must consider the surrounding context, incorporating social, cultural, environmental, and historical factors. This understanding is crucial when integrating sustainable strategies, especially in urban environments or existing

structures. Designers are encouraged to adopt adaptable solutions that respect the unique characteristics of their locales[8].

Multi-Faceted Approach

Sustainable design is inherently multifaceted, necessitating a balance between environmental, economic, and social factors. For instance, while an energy-efficient design may benefit the environment, it must also be economically viable and socially acceptable. Therefore, considering multiple perspectives during the design process is vital to developing holistic solutions that benefit both the community and the environment[8].

Long-Term Sustainability

The principles of sustainable design have evolved from theoretical concepts to practical necessities in architectural education. Students preparing for accreditation exams must demonstrate their ability to apply these principles in various design scenarios, highlighting the importance of understanding sustainable materials and construction techniques. This focus on sustainability not only prepares students for academic assessments but also equips them for real-world challenges in architecture[8].

Embracing Change

As society adapts to new living conditions and preferences, housing design must reflect these dynamic needs. The integration of flexible and versatile layouts can accommodate varying functions throughout the day, supporting remote living and evolving lifestyles. By leveraging digitalization and responsive design principles, architects can create spaces that remain relevant and useful over time, contributing to sustainable living practices in the long run[6].

Case Studies

Community Engagement and Design Value

Case studies serve as crucial tools for understanding the relationship between community needs and the design of housing solutions. Research emphasizes the importance of community characteristics, such as public space availability, neighborhood identity, and the capacity to host guests, as vital components of residents' quality of life (QoL).[1] These characteristics inform the design process and can guide decision-making through participatory methods, fostering more equitable housing solutions that empower communities.

Technology and Aging in Place

Another significant area explored through case studies is the intersection of smart technology and caregiving for older adults. An Australian study analyzed the impact of home modifications and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies—such as automated lighting and video doorbells—on the wellbeing of older community care recipients.[9] Findings indicated that while IoT offers significant advantages for enhancing care,

it also introduces complexities that warrant further investigation. Each case study illustrated the nuanced interplay among caregiving activities, the older individual's functional capacity, and the built environment, highlighting the need for a holistic understanding of these relationships.[\[9\]](#)

Affordable Housing Solutions

In addressing the challenges of affordable housing, case studies demonstrate innovative approaches to increasing housing stock and improving accessibility. Research indicates that achieving affordable housing requires a multifaceted strategy, including modular housing solutions and incentivizing financing mechanisms tailored for low-income groups.[\[10\]](#)[\[11\]](#) The urgency of addressing these housing needs is underscored by the projection that by 2030, nearly 3 billion people will require new housing.[\[11\]](#) These studies reveal the pressing need for collaboration among architects, planners, and policymakers to create sustainable, inclusive housing that can adapt to changing urban demands.

Preserving Community Identity

The impact of intensive urban development on local identity is another focus of case studies. Such development often threatens the distinctiveness of neighborhoods, which can lead to a loss of social cohesion and overall wellbeing among residents.[\[12\]](#) Case studies highlight the benefits of preserving local identity, which can foster a more people-centered, livable urban environment. They emphasize that considerations during city regeneration must involve not only the built environment but also the residents who contribute to the cultural fabric of the community.[\[12\]](#) Through these various case studies, key factors emerge that can inform future housing design, emphasizing the need for an integrated approach that considers community engagement, technological advancements, affordability, and cultural identity.

Challenges

Housing Affordability Crisis

The global housing landscape is currently facing a significant affordability crisis, with estimates suggesting that around 1.6 billion people could be affected by inadequate and unaffordable housing within a decade[\[11\]](#). Recent data indicates that approximately 80 percent of cities worldwide lack affordable housing options for half of their populations, making affordability a central concern in urban planning and development[\[13\]](#). Factors contributing to this crisis include the increasing costs of labor and materials, as well as market forces that can inadvertently drive up demand in desirable urban locations, often leaving lower-wage earners unable to access housing[\[10\]](#).

Urban Inequalities

The lack of affordable housing exacerbates urban inequalities, forcing vulnerable populations—including low-income households, migrants, young people, and the elderly—into overcrowded and unsafe living conditions or into areas with limited

access to essential services such as employment, healthcare, and education[13][14]. This trend has been compounded by growing income instability, especially in the wake of COVID-19, which is likely to increase mortgage and rental arrears, leading to more evictions among those most in need[14].

Supply Constraints

Despite a high demand for homes, the construction supply chain remains sluggish in its ability to respond to changing market conditions. Factors such as bottlenecks in the availability of essential materials, labor shortages, and the complex regulatory environment further exacerbate this issue[15]. The lag between demand and supply creates opportunities for industry-wide changes, yet significant obstacles remain for developers trying to build affordable housing[10].

Environmental Considerations

Designing housing for the future must also account for environmental challenges, including climate change and its impact on living conditions. The integration of sustainable building materials and practices often requires a larger upfront investment, which can deter developers despite potential long-term savings[16]. Furthermore, reliance on renewable energy sources may introduce variability in energy supply, making it crucial to balance sustainability with practical considerations for consistent energy availability[17].

Social and Bureaucratic Constraints

Social housing challenges are compounded by the need for a rational administrative order that often conflicts with the organic development of informal settlements, like favelas, which typically arise in response to urgent social needs[18]. The complexity of zoning regulations, bureaucratic accountability, and the conventions surrounding private property further complicate the delivery of effective housing solutions[18]. Balancing the interests of various stakeholders—including government bodies, developers, and residents—remains a critical yet challenging aspect of modern urban housing design.

Future Trends

Technological Integration

The evolution of smart homes is significantly influenced by emerging technologies, with the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Virtual Reality (VR) acting as foundational pillars. These technologies promise to enhance daily living by automating mundane tasks, thereby freeing up time for creativity and family interactions[19][20]. The integration of advanced building controls utilizing sensors and automation can optimize energy use, improve comfort, and reduce consumption, thus enhancing the overall efficiency of smart homes[21].

Sustainable Practices

As the demand for sustainable construction grows, the construction sector is increasingly embracing innovations that prioritize eco-friendliness. Living materials, such as self-mending concrete, not only extend the life of buildings but also lower maintenance costs[21]. Furthermore, manufacturers are responding to the demand for sustainable materials, reflecting consumers' heightened awareness of environmental impacts and tighter regulations on energy consumption[22]. This shift towards sustainability is reinforced by global agreements, such as the Paris Agreement, that encourage low-carbon practices in construction[23].

Resilience to Disruptors

Future housing designs must also consider external disruptors like global pandemics, climate change, and demographic shifts. Research indicates that these factors will shape the evolution of homes over the next decade, leading to designs that are not only resilient but also adaptable to changing needs[24]. By incorporating technological advancements, designers can create homes that meet contemporary challenges while remaining efficient and sustainable[25].

Client Expectations

With the rising tech-savviness of clients, there is a growing demand for modern technologies in new home construction. Clients and professionals alike are increasingly seeking state-of-the-art solutions that enhance safety, optimize builds, and ensure more durable structures[25]. This trend towards advanced construction technology is seen as a necessity for staying competitive and meeting the evolving expectations of homeowners[23].

The Future Landscape

As the landscape of housing design continues to evolve, it is essential for designers and builders to stay abreast of innovations that push the boundaries of what is possible. The focus will not only be on technological integration but also on fostering a harmonious relationship between nature, technology, and well-being—ensuring that future homes are a blend of efficiency, sustainability, and livability[6][20].

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